

PARTITIONS OF NATURAL NUMBERS AND THEIR REPRESENTATION FUNCTIONS

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Abstract

For a given set A of nonnegative integers the representation functions $R_2(A, n)$, $R_3(A, n)$ are defined as the number of solutions of the equation $n = x + y$, $x, y \in A$ with condition $x < y$, $x \leq y$, respectively. In this note we are going to determine the partitions of natural numbers into two parts such that their representation functions are the same from a certain point onwards.

1. Introduction

Throughout this paper we use the following notations: let \mathbb{N} be the set of nonnegative integers. For $A \subset \mathbb{N}$ let $R_1(A, n)$, $R_2(A, n)$, $R_3(A, n)$ denote the number of solutions of

$$\begin{aligned} x + y &= n & x, y \in A \\ x + y &= n & x < y, \quad x, y \in A \\ x + y &= n & x \leq y, \quad x, y \in A \end{aligned}$$

respectively. A Sárközy asked whether there exist two sets A and B of nonnegative integers with infinite symmetric difference, i.e.

$$|(A \cup B) \setminus (A \cap B)| = \infty$$

and

$$R_i(A, n) = R_i(B, n) \quad n \geq n_0$$

for $i = 1, 2, 3$. For $i=1$ the answer is negative (see [2]). For $i = 2$ G. Domby (see [2]) and for $i = 3$ Y. G. Chen and B. Wang (see [1]) proved that the set of nonnegative integers

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can be partitioned into two subsets A and B such that $R_i(A, n) = R_i(B, n)$ for all $n \geq n_0$. In this note we determine the sets $A \subset \mathbb{N}$ for which either

$$R_2(A, n) = R_2(\mathbb{N} \setminus A, n) \quad \text{for } n \geq n_0$$

or

$$R_3(A, n) = R_3(\mathbb{N} \setminus A, n) \quad \text{for } n \geq n_0.$$

Theorem 1. *Let N be a positive integer. The equality $R_2(A, n) = R_2(\mathbb{N} \setminus A, n)$ holds for $n \geq 2N - 1$ if and only if $|A \cap [0, 2N - 1]| = N$ and $2m \in A \Leftrightarrow m \in A$, $2m + 1 \in A \Leftrightarrow m \notin A$ for $m \geq N$.*

Setting out from $N = 1$ and $0 \in A$ we get Dombi's construction which is the set of nonnegative integers n where in the binary representation of n the sum of the digits is even.

Theorem 2. *Let N be a positive integer. The equality $R_3(A, n) = R_3(\mathbb{N} \setminus A, n)$ holds for $n \geq 2N - 1$ if and only if $|A \cap [0, 2N - 1]| = N$ and $2m \in A \Leftrightarrow m \notin A$, $2m + 1 \in A \Leftrightarrow m \in A$ for $m \geq N$.*

Setting out from $N = 1$ and $0 \in A$ we get Y. G. Chen and B. Wang's construction which is the set of nonnegative integers n where in the binary representation the number of the digits 0 is even.

2. Proofs

The proofs are very similar therefore we only present here the proof of Theorem 2.

Proof of Theorem 2. For $A \subset \mathbb{N}$ let

$$f(x) = \sum_{a \in A} x^a = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \epsilon_i x^i.$$

Then we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} R_3(A, n)x^n = \frac{1}{2}(f(x^2) + f^2(x))$$

and

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} R_3(\mathbb{N} \setminus A, n)x^n = \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{1}{1-x^2} - f(x^2) + \left(\frac{1}{1-x} - f(x)\right)^2\right),$$

moreover the condition $R_3(A, n) = R_3(\mathbb{N} \setminus A, n)$ for $n \geq 2N - 1$ is equivalent to the existence of a polynomial $p(x)$ of degree at most $2N - 2$ such that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (R_3(A, n) - R_3(\mathbb{N} \setminus A, n))x^n = p(x).$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (R_3(A, n) - R_3(\mathbb{N} \setminus A, n))x^n = \\ & \frac{1}{2}(f(x^2) + f^2(x) - (\frac{1}{1-x^2} - f(x^2) + (\frac{1}{1-x} - f(x))^2)) = \\ & \frac{1}{2}(2f(x^2) - \frac{1}{1-x^2} - \frac{1}{(1-x)^2} - \frac{2f(x)}{1-x}) = \\ & f(x^2) - \frac{1}{(1-x)^2(1+x)} + \frac{f(x)}{1-x} = p(x), \end{aligned}$$

i.e.

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1-x^2} - f(x^2) + f(x^2)x + p(x)(1-x).$$

First let us suppose that $R_3(A, n) = R_3(\mathbb{N} \setminus A, n)$ holds for $n \geq 2N - 1$. Then there exists a polynomial $p(x)$ of degree at most $2N - 2$ such that

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1-x^2} - f(x^2) + f(x^2)x + p(x)(1-x).$$

So we have

$$p(x)(1-x) = \sum_{i=0}^{2N-1} \alpha_i x^i,$$

where $\sum_{i=0}^{2N-1} \alpha_i = 0$, furthermore

$$\frac{1}{1-x^2} - f(x^2) + f(x^2)x = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} ((1-\epsilon_i)x^{2i} + \epsilon_i x^{2i+1}).$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \epsilon_i x^i = \\ & \frac{1}{1-x^2} - f(x^2) + f(x^2)x + p(x)(1-x) = \\ & \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} ((1-\epsilon_i)x^{2i} + \epsilon_i x^{2i+1}) + \sum_{i=0}^{2N-1} \alpha_i x^i + \sum_{i=N}^{\infty} ((1-\epsilon_i)x^{2i} + \epsilon_i x^{2i+1}) = \\ & \sum_{i=0}^{2N-1} \epsilon_i x^i + \sum_{i=2N}^{\infty} \epsilon_i x^i, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\sum_{i=0}^{2N-1} \epsilon_i = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} ((1-\epsilon_i) + \epsilon_i) + \sum_{i=0}^{2N-1} \alpha_i = N,$$

therefore

$$|A \cap [0, 2N - 1]| = N$$

and

$$\epsilon_{2m} = 1 - \epsilon_m, \quad \epsilon_{2m+1} = \epsilon_m \quad \text{for } m \geq N,$$

which means that $2m \in A$ if and only if $m \notin A$ and $2m + 1 \in A$ if and only if $m \in A$ for $m \geq N$, which proves the necessary part of Theorem 2.

In the sufficient part we assume that $|A \cap [0, 2N - 1]| = N$ and $2m \in A \Leftrightarrow m \notin A$, $2m + 1 \in A \Leftrightarrow m \in A$ for $m \geq N$. This is equivalent to the assumptions that for the generating function $f(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \epsilon_i x^i$ we have

$$\sum_{i=0}^{2N-1} \epsilon_i = N$$

and

$$\epsilon_{2m} = 1 - \epsilon_m, \quad \epsilon_{2m+1} = \epsilon_m \quad \text{for } m \geq N.$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \epsilon_i x^i = \sum_{i=0}^{2N-1} \epsilon_i x^i + \sum_{i=N}^{\infty} \epsilon_{2i} x^{2i} + \sum_{i=N}^{\infty} \epsilon_{2i+1} x^{2i+1} = \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{2N-1} \epsilon_i x^i + \sum_{i=N}^{\infty} (1 - \epsilon_i) x^{2i} + \sum_{i=N}^{\infty} \epsilon_i x^{2i+1} = \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{2N-1} \epsilon_i x^i + \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (1 - \epsilon_i) x^{2i} - \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (1 - \epsilon_i) x^{2i} + \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \epsilon_i x^{2i+1} - \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \epsilon_i x^{2i+1} = \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} x^{2i} - \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \epsilon_i x^{2i} + x \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \epsilon_i x^{2i} + \sum_{i=0}^{2N-1} \epsilon_i x^i - \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (1 - \epsilon_i) x^{2i} - \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \epsilon_i x^{2i+1} = \\ &= \frac{1}{1-x^2} - f(x^2) + x f(x^2) + \sum_{i=0}^{2N-1} \gamma_i x^i, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\sum_{i=0}^{2N-1} \gamma_i = \sum_{i=0}^{2N-1} \epsilon_i - \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (1 - \epsilon_i) - \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \epsilon_i = N - N = 0,$$

therefore there exists a polynomial $p(x)$ of degree at most $2N-2$ such that

$$\sum_{i=0}^{2N-1} \gamma_i x^i = p(x)(1-x).$$

Hence

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1-x^2} - f(x^2) + f(x^2)x + p(x)(1-x),$$

which proves the sufficient part of Theorem 2.

References

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